

Increased Selectivity for Planar Chromatography by Ion Exchange : Ion Chromatography on Papers impregnated with Stannic Antimonate and Stannic Arsenate

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Chromatography on papers impregnated with inorganic ion exchangers affords the possibility of achieving important separations of metal ions in aqueous and mixed solvent systems due to the increased selectivity. The antimonate and arsenate of tin(IV) possess unusual properties as inorganic ion exchangers. Stannic antimonate and stannic arsenate have been successfully utilised in paper chromatography¹, electrochromatography² and thin layer chromatography³. Stannic arsenate papers were found to be selective for Cr³⁺ in complex forming acid systems⁴. However, the effect of pH and the composition of solvent on various chromatographic parameters for metal ions have not been studied. Dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) has a fairly high dielectric constant ($\epsilon = 47.5$). Water-miscible liquid has proved to be a selective solvent for many organic and even polymeric compounds, and can enter into H-bonding and dipole-dipole association. This prompted us to use it as a solvent for thin layer chromatography of metal ions⁵. Aqueous HNO₃ and DMSO-HNO₃ systems were chosen as solvents. DMSO was also used for quantitative separation of Pd²⁺ by paper chromatography⁶. Ion chromatography was also performed on Whatman no. 1 papers. The effect of pH on R_i , $\log R_f$ and R_m values in aqueous systems has been examined. Besides, the modified form of Lederer's equation : $-n \log a_{Na^+} = R_m + \text{constant}$, where n stands for the charge on the metal ion, a_{Na^+} is the activity of Na⁺ ions in the solvents containing increasing concentrations of a_{Na⁺} ions and $R_m = \log (1/R_f) - 1$ has been verified.

Results and Discussion

Chromatography of fortyeight metal ions was performed on stannic antimonate and stannic arsenate papers in the following solvent systems : HNO₃ (10⁻⁵–4.0 M), DMSO (100%), DMSO + 0.1 M HNO₃ (1 : 1), DMSO + 0.5 M HNO₃ (1 : 1), DMSO + 1.0 M HNO₃ (1 : 1), DMSO + 3.0 M HNO₃ (1 : 1) and demineralised water. The same solvent systems were also used on plain papers for comparison. Chromatography was also performed on stannic antimonate and stannic arsenate papers in Na⁺-form in various NaNO₃ solutions of 0.5–4.0 M concentrations in order to verify the Lederer's equation in its modified form. Representative R_f values of metal ions in some of the solvents are given in Table 1. In pure DMSO, the R_f values on antimonate papers are much higher than that on arsenate papers, which can be attributed to the fact that the arsenate papers are slightly more ionised than antimonate ones. Antimonic acid has a pK_a value of 2.34–3.18, while arsenic acid has pK_a 2.25. This view is supported by the fact that when we compare the two papers in DMSO + 1 M HNO₃ (1 : 1), then the difference between these two papers diminishes. The few exceptions are Cr³⁺, Fe²⁺, Fe³⁺ and Bi³⁺. These ions have very low R_f values on stannic arsenate papers probably due to chemical interaction with the paper matrix.

Earlier, we defined a new quantity R_i ($R_i = R_f$ on plain papers minus R_f on impregnated papers) proposed as a measure of the ion exchange effect¹.

TABLE I— R_f VALUES OF METAL IONS IN SOME SOLVENT SYSTEMS ON STANNIC ARSENATE, STANNIC ANTIMONATE AND WHATMAN NO. 1 PAPERS*

Metal ion	Stannic arsenate									Stannic antimonate			Whatman no.1		
	S_1	S_2	S_3	S_4	S_5	S_6	S_7	S_8	S_9	S_6	S_7	S_8	S_6	S_7	S_8
Al ³⁺	0.11	0.13	0.41	0.48	0.81	0.00	0.20	0.70	0.11	0.45	T	0.96	0.10	0.25	0.95
K ⁺	0.59	0.70	0.86	0.84	0.90	0.20	0.34	0.66	0.59	0.26	0.52	0.75	0.16	0.28	0.70
Ca ²⁺	0.23	0.46	0.78	0.86	0.79	0.05	0.00	0.80	0.05	0.65	0.97	0.90	0.20	0.25	0.93
VO ²⁺	0.10	0.08	0.69	0.47	0.87	0.00	0.50	0.80	0.12	0.46	0.97	0.95	0.95	0.90	0.90
Mn ²⁺	0.26	0.06	0.80	0.85	0.82	0.00	0.46	0.70	0.25	0.92	0.95	0.90	0.15	0.35	0.92
Fe ³⁺	0.10	0.07	0.22	0.31	0.36	0.10	0.05	0.15	0.12	0.00	0.05	0.96	0.16	0.40	0.90
Co ²⁺	0.13	0.33	0.86	0.81	0.90	0.08	0.26	0.70	0.15	0.00	0.14	0.91	0.25	0.35	0.90
Ni ²⁺	0.16	0.34	0.75	0.80	0.83	0.06	0.10	0.75	0.10	0.45	T	0.89	0.20	0.45	0.92
Cu ²⁺	0.08	0.07	0.77	0.77	0.87	0.00	0.32	0.80	0.10	0.15	0.11	0.35	0.12	0.40	0.92
Zn ²⁺	0.21	0.21	0.78	0.82	0.85	0.00	0.80	0.90	0.25	0.90	0.97	0.92	0.16	0.35	0.92
Rb ⁺	0.45	0.76	0.84	0.85	0.86	0.20	0.31	0.60	0.50	0.10	0.41	0.75	0.20	0.40	0.70
Sr ²⁺	0.29	0.41	0.81	0.86	0.93	0.10	0.29	0.70	0.30	0.70	0.84	0.82	0.96	0.90	0.92
Y ³⁺	0.23	0.19	0.50	0.94	0.90	0.00	0.40	0.70	0.25	0.95	T	0.92	0.20	0.80	0.92
ZrO ²⁺	0.12	0.07	0.05	0.11	0.17	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.15	0.05	T	0.40	0.10	0.02	0.10
MoO ₄ ²⁻	0.77	0.95	0.92	0.19	0.27	0.00	0.00	0.90	0.85	0.00	0.03	0.09	0.45	0.50	0.90
Ag ⁺	0.23	0.10	0.15	0.40	0.17	0.80	0.00	0.00	0.25	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.38	0.09	0.10
Cd ²⁺	0.26	0.25	0.77	0.84	0.84	0.10	0.28	0.75	0.30	0.95	0.98	0.95	0.97	0.95	0.92
In ³⁺	0.15	0.03	0.16	0.45	0.65	0.00	0.09	0.65	0.11	0.00	0.04	0.97	0.10	0.42	0.90
Sb ³⁺	0.08	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.11	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.06	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	0.25	0.45	0.85
Cs ⁺	0.49	0.60	0.86	0.86	0.93	0.20	0.30	0.55	0.50	0.05	0.45	0.70	0.15	0.30	0.62
Ba ²⁺	0.14	0.31	0.63	0.77	0.78	0.10	0.26	0.80	0.19	0.65	0.92	0.78	0.90	0.95	0.90
La ³⁺	0.28	0.16	0.78	0.87	0.81	0.10	0.40	0.90	0.25	0.70	T	0.89	0.20	1.00	0.92
Ce ³⁺	0.42	0.28	0.47	0.84	0.79	0.05	0.30	0.70	0.45	0.72	0.15	0.90	0.10	0.48	0.92
Pt ⁴⁺	0.73	0.84	0.91	0.90	0.82	0.65	0.43	0.80	0.80	0.90	0.95	0.90	0.90	0.90	0.92
Hg ²⁺	0.34	0.35	0.61	0.83	0.75	0.80	0.77	0.91	0.35	0.90	0.97	0.96	0.10	0.00	0.92
Tl ⁺	0.19	0.25	0.68	0.77	0.70	0.10	0.30	0.33	0.15	0.15	0.05	0.10	0.10	0.80	0.70
Pb ²⁺	0.41	0.22	0.29	0.74	0.81	0.05	0.32	0.70	0.45	0.05	0.05	0.08	0.95	0.95	0.92
Th ⁴⁺	0.06	0.15	0.27	0.44	0.50	0.05	0.31	0.35	0.10	0.45	T	0.92	0.90	1.00	0.90
UO ₂ ²⁺	0.14	0.25	0.27	0.47	0.60	0.00	0.52	0.85	0.06	0.85	0.96	0.93	0.20	0.44	0.90
WO ₄ ²⁻	0.78	0.96	0.90	0.34	0.14	0.00	0.85	0.90	0.97	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.61	0.90
TiO ²⁺	0.04	0.06	0.08	0.22	0.29	0.02	0.00	0.20	0.10	0.44	0.00	0.25	0.18	0.45	0.90
Cr ³⁺	0.19	0.10	0.72	0.90	0.87	0.08	0.02	0.09	0.18	0.95	T	0.96	0.10	0.40	0.95

*N.D. = Not detected; T = Tailing. $S_1 = 10^{-5} M$ HNO₃; $S_2 = 10^{-2} M$ HNO₃; $S_3 = 10^{-1} M$ HNO₃; $S_4 = 1 M$ HNO₃; $S_5 = 3 M$ HNO₃; $S_6 =$ DMSO; $S_7 =$ DMSO + 0.1M HNO₃ (1 : 1); $S_8 =$ DMSO + 1M HNO₃ (1 : 1); $S_9 =$ DMW.

Effect of pH on R_i values of metal ions in aqueous HNO₃ systems was studied. From R_i vs pH plots, it is observed that R_i increases with the rise in pH for both type of papers and becomes maximum at pH 2, the steep rise being between pH 1 and 2. Thus pH 2 is the most optimum acidity for ion exchange. However, R_i is maximum at pH zero for ZrO²⁺, HfO²⁺ and Bi³⁺ which can be attributed to excessive hydrolysis of Bi³⁺ in acidic media and formation of insoluble arsenates of ZrO²⁺ and HfO²⁺. The R_i values are higher for stannic antimonate papers than stannic arsenate papers, confirming that

stannic arsenate is a weak cation exchanger. The R_m values were found to be linearly dependent on pH.

The effect of the mole fractions of HNO₃ on the R_f values of metal ions is shown by the plot of R_f vs (mole fraction of HNO₃)^{1/2} in the eluants. For K⁺, Rb⁺ and Cs⁺ a simple relationship, $R_f = a + b$ (mole fraction HNO₃)^{1/2} holds good. This relationship is particularly useful since for K⁺, Rb⁺ and Cs⁺, the R_f values are almost the same for Whatman no. 1 and im-

TABLE 2—PRECIPITATION OF CATIONS IN MIXTURES OF SOLVENT AND IMPREGNATING MATERIAL*

Solvent	Cation + Solvent		Cation + sodium arsenate + Solvent		Cation + potassium antimonate + Solvent	
	P	NP	P	NP	P	NP
Demineralised water			$\text{UO}_2^{2+}, \text{Ni}^{2+}$	$\text{VO}^{2+}, \text{Pd}^{2+}$	Pb^{2+}	
1 M HNO_3	MoO_4^{2-} WO_4^{2-}	None			$\text{Ag}^+, \text{Tl}^+, \text{Pb}^{2+}$	Fe^{3+}
DMSO	None	Hg^{2+}	Ni^{2+}	None	$\text{Ag}^+, \text{Tl}^+, \text{Pb}^{2+}$	Fe^{3+}
DMSO + 0.1M HNO_3 (1 : 1)	None	Ag^+	$\text{Ca}^{2+}, \text{Ag}^+$	None	$\text{Ag}^+, \text{Tl}^+, \text{Pb}^{2+}$	Fe^{3+}
DMSO + 0.5M HNO_3 (1 : 1)	None	ZrO^{2+}	Ag^+	Ga^{3+}	$\text{Ag}^+, \text{Tl}^+, \text{Pb}^{2+}$	
DMSO + 1M HNO_3 (1 : 1)	None	Ag^+	Ag^+	Cr^{3+}	$\text{Ag}^+, \text{Pb}^{2+}$	
DMSO + 3M HNO_3 (1 : 1)			$\text{Th}^{4+}, \text{ZrO}^{2+}$	Cr^{3+}	$\text{Ag}^+, \text{Pb}^{2+}$	

*P = cations which precipitate; N.P. = cations which do not precipitate.

pregnated papers. For other ions, this relationship does not hold good as DMSO being a complexing agent, interacts with most of the cations.

In order to verify the Lederer's equation in its modified form, the stannic antimonate and stannic arsenate papers were prepared in Na^+ -form and then used for chromatography of metal ions using NaNO_3 solutions of different concentrations as the solvent. Plots of R_m vs $(-\log a_{\text{Na}^+})$ for K^+ , Rb^+ , Cs^+ , Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} on stannic arsenate papers were found to be linear and the slope depends upon the charge of the cation studied. Thus stannic arsenate papers obey the Lederer's equation in the modified form. The same relationship holds good for stannic antimonate papers too.

The zero R_f values for a number of cations on Whatman no.1 and impregnated papers may be due to strong adsorption, precipitation or ion exchange. On mixing solution of the cation with mobile phase, a precipitate was obtained for MoO_4^{2-} and WO_4^{2-} . In such cases, the zero R_f on plain papers is therefore due to the precipitation mechanism. The zero R_f for Ag^+ , Hg^{2+} or ZrO^{2+} may be either due to interaction with the paper matrix or strong adsorption. In order to simulate conditions on stannic arsenate impregnated papers, the sodium salt of the anion was added to the cation solution followed by the solvent. Under these conditions UO_2^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Ag^+ , Th^{4+} and ZrO^{2+} are precipitated (Table 2).

For these cations the precipitation mechanism holds good. The zero R_f of Cr^{3+} is due to its tendency to be held tenaciously on cation exchanger so that it is not easily desorbed⁷. For stannic antimonate papers, the zero R_f for Ag^+ , Tl^+ and Pb^{2+} is due to precipitation. Fe^{3+} is selectively adsorbed on these papers causing zero R_f .

In pure DMSO, the separation of Cd^{2+} from Zn^{2+} or Mn^{2+} , Ca^{2+} from Mg^{2+} and TiO^{2+} from VO^{2+} were achieved on plain papers. On stannic arsenate papers, the separation of Cr^{3+} from MoO_4^{2-} or WO_4^{2-} , MoO_4^{2-} from UO_2^{2+} or VO^{2+} and ZrO^{2+} from Th^{4+} and a mixture of rare earths were effected. Synthetic alloy samples of Cr^{3+} with Zn^{2+} , Mn^{2+} and Al^{3+} were separated on these papers.

Experimental

Whatman no. 1 paper strips (16 × 3.6 cm) were used in glass jar (20 × 5 cm).

Stannic chloride pentahydrate (P.P.H., Poland), potassium antimonate (B.D.H.) and sodium arsenate heptahydrate (Riedel) were used. All other chemicals were of AnalaR grade. The test solutions (generally 0.1 M of the metal nitrate or chloride) were prepared as described earlier¹. Conventional spot test reagents were used for detection purpose.

Stannic arsenate papers were prepared as reported earlier¹. Similar procedure was followed to prepare

stannic antimonate papers. The papers in Na⁺-form were prepared by dipping in a solution of NaNO₃ of required concentration after depositing stannic antimonate or arsenate. The ion exchange capacity of the impregnated papers was determined by column experiments (saturation method). For K⁺ ion (K⁺-H⁺ exchange), the ion exchange capacity for stannic arsenate papers was found to be 0.36 meq/g of treated papers. For stannic antimonate papers, the value of ion exchange capacity was 0.32 meq/g of treated paper.

Procedure : Test solution (0.02 ml) containing 2×10^{-6} moles of the ions was placed on the paper with a thin glass capillary. The paper was then conditioned for 10 min and dipped in solvent until the ascent was 11 cm. The R_f values of spots were measured.

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